

Hayagriva - Madhava Temple at Hajo

A study of the late medieval temple style of Koch Ruler, Assam

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Abstract

From the Gupta period onwards, Assam has a distinct history of temple construction, however most of the early temples have either collapsed or are in a damaged state. The Ahom period, when the Ahom kings showed tremendous effort in erecting many temples, is remembered as the most prosperous period of temple construction in Assam. During the late medieval period, a great number of temples were constructed in this region. Following the Ahom dynasty, the Koch kings ruled Assam for a while and were responsible for the construction of a number of temples in the Brahmaputra valley. The Koch rulers' construction works were limited to the districts of Goalpara, Kamrup, and Darrang. The two most important Koch temples that have survived are the Kamakhya temple and the Hayagriva- Mahadeva temple. The main objective of this paper is to examine the architectural characteristics of the Hayagriva- Mahadeva temple in Hajo, Kamrup district.

Key Words: Temple architecture, Late medieval, Koch ruler, Hayagriva- Mahadeva temple, Assam

Introduction

Assam has a unique history of temple buildings from Gupta period onwards though most of the early temples have either completely disappeared or they are in a dilapidated condition. The fragmented structural parts of these ruined temples are still seen to exist in form of door- jams *amalakas* lintels, door sills and others which help us to know the architectural pattern of the early temples. Among these ruined structures, the door frame of Da- parvatiya, in the vicinity of the modern town of Tezpur is note-worthy (Choudhury, 1985:170). It is from these structural parts that one can easily understand the contemporary architectural style of early period. The most flourishing phase of temple construction in Assam is marked by the Ahom period when the Ahom rulers took great initiative for building different temples. A large number of temples were built during the late medieval period. This period witnessed the growth of a new architectural style which has been termed as “Nilachala type” representing Assam’s own regional temple style. Following the Ahom dynasty, the Koch rulers reigned Assam for a while and contributed to the erection of a few temples in the land of Brahmaputra valley. The building activities of the

Figure 1 Map of Assam

Koch rulers were confined to the districts of Goalpara, Kamrup and Darrang. The Kamakhya temple and the Hayagriva-Mahadeva temple are the two very significant Koch temples which have survived the test of time. The present paper aims to highlight the architectural features of the Hayagriva-Mahadeva temple at Hajo in Kamrup district (Fig.1).

In Assam, temples or shrines have different names like *dol*, *debaloy* or *than*. Assam temples can be classified into three categories from the ruined but intact structures seen today. The first group resembles the Nagara style of Orissa. The second group characterizes Assam own vernacular style- the “Nilachala type”, which has been recognized as the major architectural

pattern of Assam and is very popular in this valley. The third group reflects an unusual style having a special merit of its own. It is a combined architecture of temple and Mughal mausoleum (Sarma, 1988: 119). It is a rare architectural feature.

Temple of Hayagriva- Madhava

The Hayagriva – Madhava temple (Fig.2) is located at Hajo, a small town about thirty kilometers north-west of Gauhati. It is believed that the present temple was not built by any Koch king. It was only renovated by the Koch king Raghudeva. Probably, there was an old temple over which the present temple was built. A stone inscription attached to the temple mentions that Raghudeva reconstructed the temple in 1583 (Neog, 1974:17). This inscription also mentions that Shidhara, the architect of this temple supervised the renovation work.

Figure 2 Hayagriva – Madhava Temple

Architecturally, the temple consists of three component parts, namely sanctum cella, pillared assembly hall and a small passage (*antarala*) which connects the other two component parts (Fig.3). The Hayagriva- Madhava temple belongs to the *nagara* style but in many instances, it exhibits its regional attributes. The tower resembles the shape of a *rekha deul* with a disproportionately tapered upper part and a *bada* region which also takes an unusual taller shape. Unlike the typical Orissan temple, the vertical lines or *rekha* are very irregular in this temple structure. The main temple is *pancha ratha* in plan but the vertical lines are not so pronounced and the regions between the *anuratha* and *kanika pagas* have been corrugated into three projections in diagonal plan (Sarma, 1988:126). This is a very unusual feature, not commonly seen in the Assamese temples. Hayagriva Bishnu is worshipped as the main deity. On the left of the main deity, the images of Jagannatha and Garuda while on the right image of Basudeva are seen.

Figure 3 Plan of Hayagriva – Madhava Temple

The outer wall of the temple or *bada* region is segmented into five divisions namely- *pabhaga*, *upara jangha*, *bandhana* and *tala jangha*. Both the *janghas* are adorned with stone sculptures of varied shapes. Since these sculptures are not enshrined in proper *devakoshtha* or niche on the outer wall, it seems that *sthapati* failed to relocate the original space for keeping these sculptures and maintaining the original sequences. The *baranda* region comprises of a number of horizontal bands of lotus petal motifs along with diamond and beaded design. The tower or *shikhara* shows a sharp bend at the top giving a complete conical shape which also reflects the regional characteristic. This type of tower is quite different from the typical Orissan temple. The local builder-artist simplified the structure perhaps due to the lack of knowledge of construction of such magnificent tower (*gandi*) like that of the Orissan temple. The irregularity in the arrangement of recesses is prominent. The frontal door of the sanctum seems to have belonged to the original temple. In the lower part (*adhithana*) of the present temple, a series of elephant frieze (*gajathara*) are visible indicating that the elephants may be supporting the entire structure's weight (Fig.4). This feature is unique in its own character. It may be presumed that these elephant friezes were originally attached to the old temple (Fig.4).

Figure 4 Elephant frieze at the base

***Mandapa* or Assembly Hall**

The *mandapa* or assembly hall (Fig.5) of this temple is much larger than sanctum. It is built with blocks of stones. Inside the hall, there are four massive octagonal stone pillars(Fig. 6)with pointed arches which not only support the flat roof of the *mandapa* but bridge the span in between walls and pillars. These arches were probably innovated by the Koch ruler under the Islamic influence (Sarma, 1988:127).A beautiful *amalaka* design is seen at the base of the pillar (Fig.7). At the centre of the hall a square alter is placed for performing temple rituals and offerings. The inner part of the hall is decorated with graceful stone sculptures of devotees (Fig.8).Another notable feature on the interior wall of the *mandapa*, is the eloquent depiction of the auspicious symbol of Srivatsa and lotus which symbolizes Vishnu and Lakshmi (Fig. 6).The elevation of *mandapa* is simply the vertical extension of the outer wall without any sculptural depiction or design. The masonry of *mandapa* is ashlar without any plastering.

Figure 5 Plan of Hayagriva Nat Mandir

Figure 6 Octagonal pillar

Figure 7 Amalaka Pillar base

Figure 8 Sculpture of Devotee

Figure 9 Srivatsaand lotus symbol

Sculptures

A number of stone sculptures and decorations adorn the exterior walls of the temple. Both *upara jangha* and *tala jangha* are replete with images of Brahmanical gods and goddess. The deities are Hayagriva Vishnu, Vishnu mounted on Garuda, Kali and others. The four handed Hayagriva image holds a mace in his upper right hand while a disc like *chakra* is held in his upper left hand. The lower right hand is evidently clutching the lotus stem, while the lower left hand is in varada mudra (Fig.10). Another image of Vishnu mounted on his *vahana* Garuda and accompanied by goddess Lakshmi is noteworthy (Fig.11). A four handed image of goddess kali holding *kharga* and shield in her two upper hands is ornately sculpted on the outer wall of the temple (Fig.12). Among the many sculptures, we also come across one portraying a horse rider with his right hand grasping a branch of foliage and his left hand holding a banner. Yet another sculpture depicts two masculine figures seated on a makara being pulled by three horses (Fig. 13). There are other male and female deities, beautifully carved on the walls. Admittedly, these images express different stylistic idioms and artistic skills of the then sculptors.

Figure 10 Image of Hayagriva Vishnu.

Figure 11 Vishnu on Garuda

Figure 12 Image of Kali

Figure13 Two male figures on Makara

Conclusion

According to the inscription, this temple was dedicated to Hayagriva- Madhava (Neog, 1974) who happens to be one of the *Avatara* forms of lord Vishnu. Vishnudarmottara Purana mentions Hayagriva – Vishnu as an incarnated form of half man and half animal (Varadpande, 2009:16). The shrine was offered by Raghudeva Narayana in 1583 who reconstructed the temple during his reign. The inscription also mentions that the temple was destroyed by the Muslim attack. According to the Devi Purana, a demon named Hayagriva was granted the blessing of not being slain by any man or animal. So, at the request of the other gods, Vishnu took on the appearance of a half-man, half-horse and vanquished the demon. Vishnu was given the name Hayagriva-Vishnu as a result of this incident. Hayagriva has been considered as a minor *avatara* form of Vishnu. (Rao, 1993:260)

In Gauhati region only two temples of Kochs have survived. These are the famous Kamakhya temple built by Koch king Naranarayan and the Hayagriva Madhava temple by Raghudeva. In fact, both of these temples were reconstructed in sixteenth century by the Koch rulers. The Koch emperors added several unique architectural elements to the Hayagriva temple. Unfortunately, the new characteristics of the temple did not attract the builders in the subsequent periods which resulted in a complete discontinuation of this architectural style.

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